

INCREASING THE INTEREST OF THE YOUNG PEOPLE IN FINE LITERATURE AND INVITING THEM TO STUDY THE WORKS OF OUR JADIDI ANCESTORS

Matkarimova Feruzabonu Alijon qizi

OSHMU student

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ABSTRACT

This article is aimed at the widespread dissemination of literary criticism among young people, to arouse their interest in reading. The article seeks to awaken love for literature and the motherland by teaching the works of Jadids.

Since the beginning of the last century, many works of art, science and drama have been created. Khojanazar Huvaydo, Uvaysi wrote a series of ghazals. Not a day goes by that we don't read and discuss a work of art. At a time when times are changing rapidly, some technical means are doing what people want to do. In ancient times, a letter was sent by pigeon or courier, in which the wait is a little longer, which can be done quickly with the help of modern devices. But these techniques cannot replace fiction. When we turn to the literature of the last century, we look at the lives of great writers Odil Yakubov, Utkir Hoshimov, Olmas Umarbekov, Abdulla Aripov, Muhammad Yusuf, Oybek, Hamid Olimjon, Said Ahmad, Abdulla Qahhor, Pirmkul Kadyrov, Uncle Murod. when we put it down, are not the great literary legacies they have created and written off dust on the shelf?

Perhaps that was their age-old dream; The "aching teeth" are crying from us, and

"Ayajonlarim" is crying, and when people are "sick", they want to eat "Ice Cream". "The stars will burn forever" when "You are great, my homeland" agrees with us, "Nido" said "Life in a dream", "Between two doors" so that the days we dreamed of will not remain. "Mirzo Ulugbek" Our grandfather also dreamed about these days sitting under the "Plane Tree". If someone catches the "History of the Four Nations" and sends it to "Steel wants to plant a hundred saplings", "Muqaddas" will be upset. Imasmikin? Abdullah Qahhor said, "Whoever has heard of the cemetery has heard it. Unsin has heard that the cemetery is as horrible in his mind on a windy night as it is in his mind, but it is still alive." The horror of the graveyard of the dead was invisible to him in the face of the horror of this place, "said teacher Said Ahmad." "How is our dog, believe it or not, I picked nine tons of cotton on the first day, I know this dog," his satires full of laughter.

When we turn to modern Uzbek literature, Ulugbek Hamdam, keeping the "Balance", listened to IqbolMirzo's "Bonu" and lamented about the young people who are indifferent to reading some books today, JavlonJovliyev said: Fear not, "said the dear reader," A thousand rays of the sun "will give us golden rays. Compiling modern and national classics of Uzbek literature into English, Russian, and Korean (poetry, qatra, badia...) today, it will be available to readers in a holistic format. During the recent meetings of the two leaders with Kyrgyzstan and our President, various agreements, resolutions and agreements were signed between the two countries. During the visit of the President of Kyrgyzstan Sadir Japarov to Tashkent; "I was very ashamed when I went to Uzbekistan, 40-50 years ago." So, since the introduction of the five initiatives, there have been many milestones in the development, support of young people in all directions, further development of our country, the greatness left by our ancestors, gathered in the neighborhood, district and regional administrations where each of us lives. If theatrical troupes are organized throughout the republic on the basis of theatrical centuries, what is the wonder of the worldview of young people, the younger generation, great confidence in the future, the foundation of the future that our ancestors expect from us?

Mahmudhoja Behbudi, who was famous at that time, spoke about "Padarkush" or the situation of an uneducated child. Our Jadid grandfather made it clear that an uneducated child would become a murderer of his father and that society would be wrapped in its own shell. Hamza Hakimzoda Nizami's "Poisonous Life or Victims of Love" youth's love, ignorance, ignorance, parents' misunderstanding of their children, Abdullah Avloni's "Literature or National Poems" series also helped the nation to rest, emigration, life The motto of the words that we, the nation, are tired of the spirit-useless body. AvazOtar or 50 lashes will be beaten according to the khan's order for these views. , how true he was. Even Muhammad Sharif Sufizadeh's call to "debons who do not appreciate you, nightingales and quails with a pot, read well, you read too, mothers" appeals to mothers who are raising the next generation. Abdurauf Fitrat 1909 He went to Istanbul to study with several of his compatriots. Due to this, Fitrat followed the path of his contemporaries, such as Ismail Gasprinsky, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Ishakhon Ibrat, Abdullah Avloni. But at that time, the tsarist government did not like the newspapers, textbooks and plays founded by all our modern ancestors. They dreamed of them in the present age in which we live. We have high hopes in our hearts to be worthy of our ancestors. In short, we are at the beginning of the path we want to take.

References:

1. Nematov H., Bozorov O. Language and speech. - T .: Teacher, 1989.
2. Mengliyev B. Modern Uzbek literary language. - Karshi: Nasaf, 2005.
3. Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language. Volume I, - T .: National of Uzbekistan encyclopedia; 2006.
4. Hojiev A. Explanatory dictionary of terms of Uzbek linguistics. -T .: Teacher, 2001
5. www.natlib.uz internet resource.